

Recent Advancement on Deep Learning in Ocular Image Analysis

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Analysis of ocular images has been a popular task since 1970s. Traditionally, low-level pixel processing and shape analysis were used to extract information from ocular images. This information was then used in if-else old style artificial intelligence (AI), known as GOF AI (good old fashioned artificial intelligence), to solve problems. By the late 1990s, a paradigm shift occurred in medical image analysis with development of supervised techniques. Inclusion of pattern recognition or machine learning into image analysis allowed the design of systems which were trained by computed using extracted features. Such systems resulted in successful commercial instruments which are still popular in AI applications. The next improvement was the invention of systems that can learn features independently. Deep learning is an approach that takes advantage of many layers to transform and input image to the output while learning increasingly higher-level information. Among deep learning methodologies, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been the most successful ones for analysis of medical and ocular images. Transformation of an image from input to output using many small-extent convolutional filters allows the network to learn features effectively. Recently, with the advancements in computer systems and development of method for efficient network training, CNNs have become the technique of choice for many image analysis tasks. In this work, a summary of recent discoveries by CNNs analysis of eye images for classification, segmentation and quality enhancement is presented. Also, an outlook for future direction of development in this field is provided.

2. Aim

To report recent advancements and discoveries in deep learning for analysis of ocular images.

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3. Material and methods

The retina is a light sensitive tissue located on the back of the eye which has a vital role in human visual perception. Several epidemic diseases such as diabetes impair retinal functions and can result in blindness if not detected and treated in a timely manner. Therefore, detection of retinal disease and abnormalities is extremely important. However, analysis of retinal images using conventional methods usually cannot pass a certain level of accuracy or provide results comparable to human experts. Recent discoveries showed that deep CNNs can overcome these limitations. CNNs comprised of several elementary processing units, each one with multiple inputs and outputs. Convolution is performed between an input with weights and the application of some nonlinearity to the output. The units are arranged on a grid, and at each layer their location corresponds to pixels of the input image. CNNs are very useful for visual processing primarily due to the spatial arrangement of the units, and secondary due to properties such as pooling, local connectivity and parameter sharing of the pooling layers. These features make CNNs a powerful tool for analysis of retinal images. Results of some of the most successful CNN based methods for analysis of ocular images for diagnosis, segmentation and quality assessment is presented in the following.

4. Results

An important goal of ocular image analysis is diseases diagnosis. Recently, Kermany et al used 200000 retinal images to show that CNNs can detect vision-threatening diseases including age-related macular degeneration (AMD) and diabetic macular edema (DME), as accurately as a panel of 7 ophthalmologists. They demonstrated that the same AI system can detect pediatric pneumonia accurately based on chest x-ray images. Interestingly, such a great result was achieved by transferring weights from an existing network of a different field rather than training a network from scratch. Similarly, Rong et al proposed a CNN that could detect AMD and DME with 100% accuracy based on retinal images from 2 different public databases.

Another highly important ocular image analysis task is vessel segmentation which is important for diagnosis and monitoring disease progression. Many vessel segmentation techniques by means of traditional image analysis and mathematical modeling have been proposed. However, their performance is limited. Specially in pathological cases where abnormal shapes are usually detected as vessels. However, deep learning based approaches can be trained to distinguish between abnormalities and true vessels. Hence, their performance has far exceeded conventional methods. Fu et al utilized a multi-scale and multi-level CNN with a side-output layer to reach a sensitivity of 0.95 which is better than the best result obtained by traditional methods on a healthy database. Likowski et al trained a CNN using 400000 retinal images and reached an accuracy of 0.97 for retinal vessel segmentation on a public dataset. This has been the highest level of accuracy reported so far for vessel segmentation on this data set.

Image quality assessment (IQA) is another important ocular image analysis task which determines whether the image quality is good enough for screening by clinicians. Traditional

IQA techniques cannot be generalized from one dataset to another since they rely heavily on accurate landmark segmentation. To address this issue, Mahapatra et al proposed a method using the principle behind human visual system using information from local saliency map and training a CNN to decide on the quality of retinal images. The evaluation tests showed that their method performs much better than available ones while being extendable to different datasets.

5. Conclusions

Deep learning has revolutionized every aspect of medical and ocular image analysis. The majority of contributions have been made over the past 2 years using end-to-end trained CNNs making it the current standard practice. However, these methods are generally referred to “black box” in clinical practice where accountability is crucial. Therefore, future work is needed to determine clinical correspondence of intermediate layers, which can increase acceptance of deep learning to clinicians and patients. Nevertheless, due to exceptional performance and presence of many unexplored applications such as ocular image reconstruction, deep learning is expected to have a great impact on the future of medical and ocular image processing.

6. Keyword

Deep learning, Medical image analysis, Eye

Author biography

Dr. Maziyar M. Khansari is a post doctorate research associate at University of Southern California (USC) working on advanced computational and learning-based medical image analysis. He completed his PhD at the age of 29 from University of Illinois at Chicago (UIC) and was awarded CCTS PECT dissertation scholarship. He has published more than 7 technical papers in reputed journals, presented at various conferences and served as a reviewer of reputable journals in his field.